

Fixation of the cup component in total shoulder arthroplasty: Evaluation of the effect of joint conformity

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ABSTRACT

Shoulder replacements usually consist of a metal convex component, as humeral head replacement, against a polyethylene cup (glenoid component) and show inferior results to hip and knee replacements, in terms of post-operative mobility and component fixation.

The glenoid reconstruction consists of an anatomical support of trabecular and cortical bone (forming a sandwich structure), an intermediate layer of PMMA (Polymethylmethacrylate, the bone-cement) and the Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene (UHMWPE) glenoid component. The interfaces in this artificial joint structure, consisting of materials of different mechanical properties, are repeatedly loaded by forces reaching several times body weight, leading to fatigue of the fixation. Within the first 5 to 10 years loosening frequently occurs, normally originating in the PMMA/bone interface.

The results of shoulder replacements depend on patient, design and surgical factors. The design factors include materials, geometry and method of fixation. The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of the radius of curvature of the glenoid component on fixation strength.

To achieve the prescribed aim, a force controlled test set-up has been developed. The joint loading, consisting of a joint compression and subluxation force (shear force), is measured by advanced force transducers, transferred to the pc and used for controlling the test set-up. The glenoid components, machined out of medical grade UHMWPE according to the geometry of a commercial available glenoid component, are cemented into synthetic bone substitutes using an alignment tool to assure a constant cement thickness. The glenoid components have radii of curvature of 25 (conform) and 29 mm and articulate against a head with radius of curvature of 25 mm. The upper and lower glenoid component rim-displacements are measured by a custom made displacement sensor and used for design comparison. Tests were performed at 2 Hz.

The conform articulation showed significant less rim-displacement compared to the non-conform articulation, with 0.299 (SD = 0.0306) and 0.350 (SD = 0.0197) mm, respectively. This might indicate that conform articulation have better fixation performance.

NOMENCLATURE

- c Glenoid centre at the articular surface,
 C Point of contact of the glenoid and humeral component for given forces,
 d_i, d_s Inferior and superior glenoid rim-displacements in medial direction,
 d_x, d_y, d_z Displacement of the centre of the humeral head in x -, y - and negative z -direction,
 F_c Contact force, directed to the centre of the humeral head,
 F_x, F_y Subluxation force acting at the centre of the humeral head in the x - and y -directions,

F_z Compression force acting at the centre of the humeral head in the z-direction, GC
Gle
noid
component,

$$\bar{M}_c = R_g \cdot (1 - \cos \varphi) \cdot F_y + R_g \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot \frac{F_z}{\tan \varphi} = R_g \cdot F_y \left(1 - \cos \varphi + \sin \varphi \cdot \frac{\cos \varphi}{\sin \varphi} \right) = R_g \cdot F_y$$

HH Humeral head component,
 M_c Tilting moment about the center of the glenoid component at the articular surface (CCW),

r_y, r_z Moment arms of F_c for M_c , in y and z-direction respectively,

R_g, R_h Radius of curvature of the glenoid and humeral component,

x, y, z Directions in the reference co-ordinate system,

φ Angle between c , the glenoid centre and C , for given forces,

κ Joint conformity (R_h/R_g),

ρ Radial clearance ($R_g - R_h$),

θ Glenoid constraint angle, angle z between the y-axis and the tangent of the glenoid rim. the artificial shoulder joint.

INTRODUCTION

Shoulder arthroplasty is a common treatment for rheumatoid and osteoarthritic patients and in case of patients with humeral fractures. The main objective is pain relief, which is achieved in most cases. Unfortunately, results in terms of increased postoperative functionality and long-term component fixation are unsatisfactory. Main complications after this treatment are shoulder subluxation and dislocation, interface micromotions, wear and finally component loosening of mainly the glenoid component [20]. These complications are influenced by patient, design and surgical factors.

Design factors include applied materials, geometrical design and method of fixation. This study is focused on one parameter of the geometrical design, i.e. the joint conformity κ . Better joint conformity leads to lower contact stresses [18] and smaller humeral head translations relative to the glenoid component [10,14]. Lower contact stresses may result in lower wear rates, whereas smaller humeral head translations lead to a more centred contact point and thus a smaller glenoid component tilting moment. With the help of a rigid body model, described in [14], the moment M_c about the glenoid centre at the articular surface c , a result of the eccentric joint contact force acting on the glenoid component, can be calculated by:

$$\bar{M}_c = -\bar{r} \cdot \bar{F}_c = r_z \cdot F_y + r_y \cdot F_z = R_g \cdot (1 - \cos \varphi) \cdot F_y + R_g \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot F_z \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

and with: eq. 2

As can be concluded from eq. 2, the tilting moment M_c is influenced by the radius of curvature R_g of the glenoid component only, for given F_y and F_z . Two Finite Element studies analysed the effect of joint conformity on stresses at the fixation. Lacroix and Prendergast (1997) analysed the cement stresses at the back side of a low and high conform glenoid component and concluded that, with respect to cement stresses, a more conform glenoid component should be used [12]. Couteau et al. (2001) also recommend a

more conform glenoid, as the decreased contact surface due to joint non-conformity leads to increased stresses at the glenoid component-cement interface [5]. From the aspects mentioned above, i.e. the lower contact stresses due to a larger contact surface, the smaller tilting moment and the lower cement stresses, it can be concluded that increased conformity might be beneficial with respect to glenoid component wear and fixation.

The tilting moment on the glenoid component, deforms the underlying bone and cement structure, which might lead to undesirable stresses at the interface. The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of joint conformity on glenoid component tilting, by means of varying the radius of curvature of the glenoid component.

Relevancy of the study

The number of hip and knee replacements, an annual amount of 259.000 and 144.000, by far exceeded the 11.000 shoulder replacements in the United States in 1997 [1]. At present, the shoulder replacement is often postponed and because of the high risk of glenoid component loosening only the humeral head is replaced. In some cases surgeons still perform a shoulder arthrodesis (rigid fixation of the proximal humerus to the lateral scapula), as the quality of the total shoulder replacement is considered inadequate. Clinical results must be improved to allow for treatment of more patients.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

A force controlled test set-up has been developed (See Figure 2), consisting of a fixation structure to the MTS 831 test system, vertical and horizontal aligned load cells and custom made support structures. The horizontal and vertical load cells measure the joint subluxation and joint compression force, applied by hydraulic and pneumatic systems, respectively.

A CoCr humeral head with a radius of curvature R_h of 25 mm is used for articulating against glenoid components, machined out of medical grade UHMWPE (Poly-Hi Solidur GmbH, Vreden, Germany), with the geometry of a commercial available keeled design. The components have superior-inferior dimension of 38.5 mm and radii of curvature R_g of 25 and

29 mm, leading to constraint angles θ of 50.35° and 41.59° , respectively (see the Nomenclature and Figure 3). Glenoid components are fixed by PMMA bone cement (Palamed G 20, Heraeus Kulzer GmbH, Wehrheim, Germany) into bone substitutes made of Polyurethane (Sawbones Europe AB, Malmö, Sweden). Two bone substitutes are used, as the Young's modulus of cancellous glenoid bone show a large range, from 99 MPa [2] to 372 MPa [13], and this might have a large effect on the glenoid rim-displacements. The two bone substitutes have a more solid, rigid morphology with stiffness and strength of 137.5 MPa and 5.4 MPa, respectively,

Figure 2 The force controlled shoulder simulator. Left: schematic overview, right the set-up integrated in the MTS test machine. 1. Glenoid component 2. Humeral head 3. Glenoid bone substitute and metal holder 4. Horizontal aligned load cell for measuring the subluxation force 5. Vertical aligned load cell for measuring the subluxation force (both: PW24C3, HBM Darmstadt, Germany) 6. Data amplifier (Peekel Instruments B.V., Rotterdam, Netherlands) 7. Constraint only allowing vertical displacements 8. Constraint only allowing horizontal displacements 9. Rodless pneumatic actuator (Festo B.V., Delft, Netherlands). 10. Hydraulic

actuator (MTS Systems Corporation, Eden Prairie, MN, U.S.A.).

and a more open cellular morphology with stiffness and strength of 260 MPa and 8.8 MPa, respectively. A custom made alignment tool has been used to assure a homogenous cement thickness of 2 mm (See Figure 5).

The glenoid components are loaded by a joint compression force of 725 ± 20 N and humeral head motion is force controlled by a cyclic subluxation force between 0 and 350 N, in superior direction. Only the superior part of the glenoid component has been loaded to better investigate the effect of tensile and compression stresses on glenoid component fixation. The loading conditions are according to All Day Living Activities, as analysed in a musculoskeletal model [8]. Five specimens have been used for the three test conditions ($R_g = 25$, $R_g = 29$ (137.5 MPa) and $R_g = 29$ (260 MPa)), which each have been measured five times after 200.000 cycles, corresponding to 44 load cases per day for 12.5 years.

In this study, glenoid rim-displacement relative to bone is correlated to glenoid fixation performance. Glenoid component loosening is thought to be due to glenoid component tilting, often referred to as glenoid component rocking, a result of eccentric loading [3,4]. Eccentric loading, for example in the superior direction, will compress the superior side of the glenoid Figure 3 The glenoid structure

with component dimensions (mm).

Figure 5 Cementing of glenoid components into bone substitutes using the aligning tool.

Figure 4 FE model, with the inferior d_i - and superior

d_s -rim displacements, positive in the z-direction.

Figure 6 Close up of the displacement sensors.

component into the glenoid bone stock and due to bone deformation, the inferior structure might undergo tensile stresses, as is also found in an FE model of the clamped glenoid component structure (28570 elements, meshed by MSC Patran 2001 r2a, materials are linear elastic and the model is analysed by MSC, Marc 2001) (See Figure 4). During testing, maximal superior and minimal inferior rim-displacements, d_s and d_i , (See Figures 3 and 4) were monitored, using custom made displacement sensors (See Figure 6).

RESULTS

The progression of the rim displacements was stable during the 200.000 cycles, as shown by the two examples in Figure 7. After 200.000 cycles complete glenoid component loosening could not be observed after inspecting the outside visually. However, rim-displacement showed clear difference between the conform and non-conform articulations (See also Table 1). The superior rim-displacement was found to be 0.299 (SD = 0.0306) and 0.350 (SD = 0.0197) for the 25 and 29 mm components, respectively, cemented in the cellular rigid bone substitute and 0.181 (SD = 0.0177) for the 29 mm glenoid component cemented into the solid rigid bone substitute. Rim-displacement was 0.051 mm larger for the non-conform glenoid components, an increase of 17%, which is significant ($p = 0.05$). Using less stiff bone substitute increased the rim-displacement by 93.4%. The inferior rim-displacement did not show this clear correlation with articular conformity, with -0.0362 mm and -0.0238 mm for the 25 mm and 29 mm components, respectively. The inferior rim-displacement was less negative for the non-conform glenoid component, showing a decrease of 34%, though this was not significant ($p = 0.05$).

Figure 7 Two examples of the glenoid rim displacements during the 200.000 cycles. d_{smax} and d_{smin} are the superior glenoid rim displacements in medial direction at maximal subluxation

force (725 N) and zero subluxation force, respectively, and d_{imax} and d_{imin} are the inferior glenoid rim displacements in medial direction at maximal subluxation force (725 N) and zero

	Maximal Superior Rim-displacement	Minimal Inferior Rim-displacement	Conditions
$R_g = 25$ mm	0.299 (0.0306)	-0.0362 (0.0133)	Cellular rigid Polyurethane bone substitute of 137.5 MPa.
$R_g = 29$ mm	0.350 (0.0197)	-0.0238 (0.0110)	
$R_g = 29$ mm	0.181 (0.0177)	-0.00306 (0.00651)	Solid rigid Poly-urethane Bone substitute of 260 MPa.

subluxation force, respectively.

Table 1 Glenoid rim-displacement in mm (average (SD)) for the conform and non-conform articulation and two types of bone substitutes.

However, in all cases, negative inferior rim-displacements were measured, indicating tensile stresses at the inferior side.

Two glenoid components with a radius of curvature of 25 and 29 mm have been tested over 1.000.000 cycles and once again complete glenoid component loosening could not be

observed after inspecting the outside visually. However, in many cases no adhesion between the UHMWPE glenoid components and the PMMA cement layer was found.

DISCUSSION

In this study the effect of joint conformity on glenoid component fixation has been investigated. A force controlled test set-up has been developed, applying physiological joint subluxation and compression forces to the glenoid components, with corresponding humeral head translations, which are a result of material deformation and radial mismatch [14]. In other studies humeral head displacements are applied [e.g. 3,16], resulting in unknown and even unrealistic forces.

Though a more conform articular joint can be an advantage for articular joints with a constant centre of rotation, this concept will not function properly in joints with a non-fixed centre of rotation, e.g. the knee joint. In this study, the natural shoulder joint kinematics is not taken into account, in particular the position of the centre of rotation during articulation, which is subject to discussion. Many studies evaluating humeral head translations relative to the glenoid cavity in the healthy shoulder conclude that the centre of rotation is fixed [6,11,17], other state that the humeral head shows small translations [e.g. 15] (See also Table 2). However, experimental results should be looked at with certain caution, as test conditions influence the results to a large extent [10]. With respect to joint kinematics, it is unclear whether or not glenoid components must have high joint conformity with the humeral head [7]. This is also stated by a clinical study, investigating the relation between radial mismatch and radiolucency score, which is related to the amount and length of radiolucent lines. Although they found an increase in radiolucency score with decreasing radial mismatch, this did not affect the glenoid fixation, in terms of clinical complications [19].

Glenoid component fixation in Total Shoulder Arthroplasty (TSA) is still an unsolved problem as is reflected by the many methods and designs for fixation. Existing methods are either cementing or bone ingrowth fixation, whereas the differences in fixation design are extensive; pegged v. keel, flat v. curved backside, smooth v. rough etc. Design details, such as grooves, holes, etc., for mechanical locking are different for almost any glenoid component on the market today. It was not our intention to solve the fixation problem of the glenoid replacement. Our aim was to investigate the effect of articular joint conformity on the fixation performance

of the glenoid component, by means of experimental testing in a force controlled test set-up.

Glenoid components are cemented in synthetic bone substitutes with mechanical properties corresponding to natural bone. However, to what extent the test conditions approximate natural

conditions, needs discussion. The components are fixated to synthetic material instead of living bone tissue and there is absence of synovial fluid. The geometry of the surrounding structure in the test set-up, consisting of a bone substitute partially (medial) clamped in a metal holder, is not as in the natural shoulder, consisting of a complex bone structure with constraints of soft tissues in a fluid environment at 37°.

Though it was found in this study that glenoid components with smaller radii of curvature and higher conformity are beneficial for glenoid component fixation, as smaller rim displacements were found, further research is necessary to examine the effect in more pathologic joints. These joints have smaller joint compression, leading to larger head translations for given subluxation force and component geometry, leading to more eccentric loading, which does not benefit to glenoid component fixation.

From literature and from personal communications it was found that more conform articulations might be beneficial for component survival, which must be validated by future research. However, component misalignment during surgery, a result of the difficult joint anatomy and pathology as well as a lack of proper alignment tools, requires component with a radial mismatch, to relieve the glenoid component from peak stresses due to the undesired enforced displaced humeral head. Therefore, future research must focus on better surgical accuracy, by the development of better alignment tools and Camera Assistant Surgery (CAS).

Though it was found that glenoid rim-displacements were smaller for conform articulations,

the effect on the residual strength has not been investigated and is part of future research. By using component pull-out or shear-out tests, this effect on component fixation must be investigated.

In this study the effect of joint conformity has been investigated, by decreasing the radius of curvature of the glenoid component from $R_g = 29$ to $R_g = 25$ mm, which, together with the increased constraint angle θ , was the only geometrical adjustment. The effect of joint conformity on glenoid component fixation, by increasing the radius of curvature of the humeral head R_h , will be smaller, as the joint contact point at the glenoid component surface, determined by the ratio of subluxation and joint compression force, is fixed. The only benefit of increased conformity by increasing humeral head radius of curvature are the more distributed contact stress and smaller joint translations. This will result in decreased wear and indirectly also in decreased component loosening rates.

Table 2 Studies focused on glenohumeral joint conformity and humeral head translations.

CONCLUSIONS

By means of experimental testing it was found that glenoid components with smaller radius of curvature, thereby better matching the humeral head, showed smaller rim-displacements compared to larger ones. The smaller displacements mean that bone deformation is smaller and this will relieve the bone-bone cement interface. As humeral head translations during shoulder motion are negligible or very small, application of conform components in Total Shoulder Arthroplasty might decrease glenoid component loosening rates.

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	Method	Radial mismatch	Joint translations
Poppen and Walker (1976) [15]	roentgenographic	High joint conformity, leading to fixed centre of rotation without excursion	1.09 ± 0.47 mm (much more in case of injured shoulders)
Severt et al. (1993) [16]	displacement controlled test	High and low mismatch	forced: 3 – 7 mm up to 6 – 13 mm
Soslowsky et al. (1992) [17]	stereophotogrammetry	High joint conformity, including cartilage	--
Kelkar et al. (2001) [11]	stereophotogrammetry	High conformity between cartilage surfaces: R_g and R_h are 24.9 and 25.0 mm.	--
Ianotti et al. (1992) [9]	adjustable contour gauge	2.3 ± 0.2 mm, after removing all soft tissues	--

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